

PEDAGOGICAL MECHANISMS OF ENSURING EFFICIENCY OF ENGLISH TEACHING

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<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10005707>

Annotation: This article talks about increasing the educational efficiency of specialists, masters and students of pedagogical institutes and pedagogical mechanisms in education also the opinions of physiologists of the Passov school are presented.

Key words: socio-economic, didactic, analysis, synthesis, reproductive.

Annotatsiya: Ushbu maqolada pedagogika institutlari mutaxasislari, magistrarlar va talabalarining o'quv samaradorligini oshirilishi hamda ta'limda pedagogik mexanizmlari haqida shuningdek Passov maktabi fiziologlarining fikrlari ham keltirilgan.

Kalit so'zlar: ijtimoiy-iqtisodiy, didaktika, analiz, sintez, reproduktiv.

Аннотация: В данной статье говорится о повышении образовательной эффективности специалистов, магистров и студентов педагогических вузов и педагогических механизмов в образовании, также представлены мнения физиологов пассовской школы

Ключевые слова: социально-экономический, дидактический, анализ, синтез, репродуктивный.

Introduction. The educational principle of education is manifested in the students' worldview, mastery of manners, development of physical strength and learning ability of students, understanding of the socio-economic policy of the state, and personality development.

In the process of education, the factors of personality formation are determined by the development and demands of society. This principle is expressed in the purposeful perception of the studied phenomena, their understanding, creative processing and application.

Consciousness, as an important principle of didactics, requires the understanding of language unity, forms, content, and their relation to existence in determining the nature of language and speech phenomena, in revealing their causal connections. The implementation of the principle of consciousness is

based on relying on the mental activity of students, their ability to use analysis and synthesis, compare and contrast, draw correct conclusions and apply knowledge in practice.

Methodological justification.

Understanding the function of language phenomena helps in the rapid development of language and speech mechanisms. Activities in teaching English mean the development of attention, thinking, memory and will in students and students, which are necessary to perform speech acts in English. The main sources of activity are goals, reasons, desires and interests.

A lack of knowledge of the language as a means of communication is noted as a disadvantage;

- the speech approach (M. Werlitz (Germany), F. Guin, P. Rivan (France), G. Suit (England), K. Freeze and R. Lado (USA)) by expressing their thoughts to the teacher allows you to express your opinion. Language learning units in the process of communication are aimed at learning speech as a method of formation and expression. The training is based on students' mastery of speech patterns, for example, typical of the field of everyday communication. Audiovisual teaching tools can be widely used in this;

- speech activity approach (B.V. Belyaev, E.I. Passov, etc.) as a type of development and improvement of speech approach from the point of view of psychological theory of activity and communicative linguistics.

The analysis of scientific sources showed that I.A.Zimnyaya revealed its specific aspects more fully.

S.F. Shatilov divides grammatical skills into morphological, morphological-syntactic and syntactic. R.P. Milrud distinguishes the speech skills and competences necessary for solving speech thinking tasks in the dialogue process, language automatisms that provide the language service of speech thinking activity. N.D. Galskova divides language skills into productive and receptive.

At the end of the 19th century, when the capitalist production method reached its most rapid development in European countries, the so-called natural method appeared in teaching foreign languages. Its founders, F.Guin, K.Berlitz, S.Krashen, M.Wolter and others, believed that in order to learn foreign languages in the educational process, first of all, it is necessary to create a similar language in the educational process. conditions for the individual (in particular, a child learning the mother tongue).

Basic material. This is the student and speech skills. Student, management of student activity by receptive, reproductive and productive types of speech activity, student, student and teacher, student speech, students' readiness to answer, ukuchi, student students determine the content of the text in advance, understand its meaning. appears in the distribution of words and phrases to find the correct tense.

The principle of exhibitionism is based on the use of the exhibition to study certain material, revive it in memory and understand the world around us.

According to the physiologists of the Passov school, an object stimulus (for example, the sound of a bell) causes an immediate reaction, a verbal stimulus (a word called a bell And 'z) is directly related to the stage that creates a link between words and words. image, imprinted in the cerebral cortex. Therefore, the purpose of using audiovisual means is to master the educational section. Of course, to make the connection between the English word and the picture, a learning-based stage related to intuition is necessary.

Thus, the purpose of using audiovisual means is to ensure the mastery of the learning unit, to create touch points to create connections between linguistic symbols and images, and to perform speech actions on the content under consideration. Visual aids differ in the level of activation of the sentence formation process, and in the future they will be completely excluded from the educational process. They are replaced by listening to materials (auditing) and unprepared (spontaneous) speech. Visualization in English language teaching is done by displaying linguistic and non-linguistic materials.

Visualization can be widely used in teaching language material and types of speech activities. According to A. A. Leontiev, there are four tasks in the spirit of expositionism:

- 1) the task of explaining local history materials;
- 2) the task of introduction by showing things, actions and events;
- 3) the task of describing problematic situations;
- 4) performs the task of teaching sentences using visual aids.

Language display (language visualization) is widely used in the methodology of teaching foreign languages by adapting the principles of visualization to the characteristics of foreign languages. This is pronunciation, reading, speaking, writing from the teacher to the students, because the teacher teaches the student, the students how to pronounce, read, write in English. When a teacher teaches pronunciation, pronunciation, speech, speech, reading, reading, writing, his writing will be an exhibition. That is why the speaker's pronunciation,

speech, reading and writing should be correct, error-free and perform the task of presentation.

External and internal signs are used in teaching English. Internal demonstrability is manifested in the comparison of the native language and the studied English language.

This view is used in conjunction with the exterior.

The principle of the sequence of teaching is determined by educational goals and educational laws. If knowledge is deeply learned and better retained in memory, such knowledge and skills can be used in later stages of education and in life. Specific characteristics of students' practical activities require systematization and consistency in teaching. The systematic principle of A.I. According to Talishkhanov, this means that the work of the teacher and the student, the activities of the students, teaching and upbringing should be in a certain system and sequence.

Conclusions. Compliance is expressed in the presentation, acquisition and working with language material. The student, the individual development characteristics of students, the characteristics of their higher nervous system activity require an individual approach to learning. An individual approach requires taking into account the student's thinking, memory, attention, life and language experience.

Communication cannot be carried out without the activity of verbal thinking provided for in the communicative direction of educational work. In such work, it is necessary to stay away from the mechanical types of work that are very common in teaching English. Thus, it is very important to stimulate students' speech and mental activity in the process of learning English.

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